

Effect of paclobutrazol on rice seedling growth^a, Gungzhou, China.

Treatment ^b (g/m ²)	Shoot ht (cm)	Width of false stem (cm)	% of seedlings with				Chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)			Rooting ability ^c (mg/plant)	
			No tiller	1 tiller	2 tillers	3 tillers	Chla	Chlb	a+b	Fresh wt of root	Dry wt of root
0	26.5	0.2	73.3	26.7	0	0	0.66	0.36	1.01	60.8	5.9
1.67	22.3	0.3	46.7	16.7	30.7	6.7	0.97	0.46	1.43	65.6	8.0
3.34	21.2	0.3	40.0	26.7	23.3	10.0	1.06	0.51	1.57	76.5	8.2

^aAt four-leaf stage. ^bGranules containing 0.6% paclobutrazol. ^cNew root growth after total removal of old roots.

Impact of level and source of slow-release N fertilizers on rice yield and yield components

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We evaluated four levels of N applied as prilled urea (PU), rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU, 31.2% N), and gypsum-coated urea (GCU, 32.2% N) during 1986 wet season. The experimental site has pH 5.5, EC 0.2 dS/m, 0.48% organic C, 24.2 kg P/ha, 49.8 kg K/ha, 0.78 ppm Zn, 1.71 ppm Cu, 40.95 ppm Fe, 0.65 ppm Mn, and 0.74 ppm B. The experiment was laid out in split-plot design.

Three 28-d-old IET3232 medium-duration seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 15 cm spacing 23 Jul 1986. PU was applied 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. Recommended 35 kg P, 73 kg K/ha, RPCU, and GCU

Effect of N source and level on grain yield and yield components of rice. ^a Mangalore, India, 1986.

Treatment	Plant height 40 DP (m)	Plant height at harvest (cm)	Tiller 40 DP (av no.)	Productive tillers at harvest (no.)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	1000- grain wt (g)	Straw yield (t/ha)
<i>Level (kg N/ha)</i>								
No N	56	81	10	8	260	4.8	21.9	4.6
37.5	64	85	12	9	312	5.1	21.8	5.8
75.0	69	90	12	10	327	5.1	22.0	(6.4)
112.5	72	89	14	9	321	5.2	22.0	7.0
CD (0.05)	6	2	2	1	24	0.2	ns	1.0
CV (%)	7	2	18	10	7	5.9	3.7	22.0
<i>Sources (S)</i>								
PU	62	87	12	9	295	5.1	22.0	5.9
RPCU	67	87	12	9	319	5.2	22.0	5.6
GCU	67	86	12	9	301	4.9	22.0	6.4
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.2	ns	ns
CV (%)	8	2	16	6	8	6.3	3.2	25.0
Interaction (L × S)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a DP = days after planting.

were applied basally. The field was flooded from transplanting to harvest and the crop protected from insects, diseases, and weeds. Harvest was 12 Nov 1986.

All yield components but 1,000-grain

weight showed a significant response to N level (see table). But responses to N sources were not similar in all characters. Slow-release N fertilizers at low levels increased grain yield in the high rainfall areas of Mangalore. □

Chemical analyses and thermal studies of azolla

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Azolla, recognized as a natural nitrogenous fertilizer for rice, barley, rye, and wheat crops, also has been recommended as a food additive in animal feeds. We report here trace element content, calorific value, and thermal decomposition studies.

Azolla pinnata and *A. microphylla* samples were collected from IRRI

ricefields, washed with distilled water, and air-dried. Trace elements were analyzed using Pye Unicam 281 and Shimadzu AA 630-01 atomic absorption spectrophotometers. X-ray fluorescence spectra were recorded on Geigerflex 3064 using Rb target (supplied by M/s. Rgaku Corporation, Japan). N analysis was done by Kjeldahl method. Calorific value was determined using Parr bomb calorimeter with correction for S. TG and DTA were recorded on Shimadzu-DT 30 simultaneous thermal analyzer.

X-ray fluorescence analysis indicated the presence of several trace elements essential for animals and plants (see

table). Quantitative analysis revealed the absence of lead, mercury, and arsenic in azolla, indicating its safety as a fodder. The heavier elements are not detected because of limitations of the target employed.

The presence of N, phosphate, and essential elements suggests azolla as a molybdenum supplement to animal feed, especially for mammalian animals such as cattle. Its calorific value of 4.84 kcal/g indicates that azolla is actively involved in metabolic pathways.

TG and DTA studies indicated that in air, azolla undergoes decomposition in four stages. In the first stage, moisture

Analytical data on *A. pinnata*. De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines.

Analysis	Method ^a	Percentage ^b
Ash		20.0
Moisture		11.0
	SP	0.015
N	Kjeldahl	3.50
Mg	AA	0.60
K	Flame emission	3.8
Ca	AA	0.60
Mn	AA	0.13
Fe	AA	0.90
Zn	AA	0.01
As	AA	0.01
As	Gutzeib (UV-vis)	ND
Mo	AA	5 × 10 ⁻⁴
Hg	Flameless AA	ND
Pb	AA	ND
PO ₄	SP	0.56
SO ₄	Turbidimetric	1.40

^a SP = spectrophotocalorimetric, AA atomic absorption. ^b ND = nondetectable.

TG and DTA of azolla. A = *A. pinnata*, B = *A. microphylla*.

loss occurs. In the second, organic components are lost, followed by decarbonization and decomposition of inorganic sulfides and carbonates. The subsequent stages yield inorganic residue. The similarities in the TG-DTA curves of *A. pinnata* and *A. microphylla* indicate that the basic matrix is similar (see figure). *A. pinnata* exhibits weight losses of 12.42, 42.55, 62.13, and 78.30% in the temperature range 80-110, 210-320, 330-425, and 435-490 °C, respectively. *A. microphylla* shows 12.15, 44.93, 66.39, and 83.40% respectively in the range 75-110, 215-315,

325-420, and 440-490 °C. The exothermic peak temperatures in the DTA curve are at 287, 305, 358, and 460 °C for *A. pinnata* and 283, 310, 353,

and 460 °C for *A. microphylla*. The first and fourth peaks indicate the major decomposition process; the second and third peaks are less intense. □

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Response of transplanted rice to micronutrients and the residual effect on wheat

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We studied the effect of Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe sulfates on yield of transplanted rice Pratap in the 1985 wet season and yield of wheat in the 1985-86 winter season. The soil and foliar applications of the micronutrients were compared with 5 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha containing 54% moisture.

Soil was silty clay loam (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 8.3, 1.303% organic matter, EC 0.22 dS/m, cation exchange capacity 24.5 meq/100 g soil, and DTPA-extractable Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe at 0.80, 15.0, 0.18, and 15.5 mg/kg soil, respectively. FYM contained 0.45% N, 0.10% P, 0.35% K, and 40,200, 69, and 1,500 mg Zn, Mn, Cu, and Fe, respectively, /kg (oven dry

basis). Treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design. Both crops received 80-17.4-33.3 kg NPK/ha in all treatments.

Soil and foliar applications of Zn and Cu increased rice yields significantly (see table). FYM with its micronutrients also increased rice yield significantly. Wheat yield was not significantly influenced by any treatment. □

Efficiency of complex fertilizers in a rice - rice farming system

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We evaluated four N sources in a randomized block design with four replications during the 1984 dry season (DS) and 1985 wet season (WS). Soil was lateritic sandy loam (pH 5.7, EC 0.115 dS/m, 0.680% organic carbon, 18 kg available P, and 150 kg available K/ ha. Rice variety Daya (120 d) was transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing. The recommended dose of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha was applied through complex mixtures A and B (18-7.86-5 kg NPK/100 kg mixture) produced by Hari Fertilizer Factory, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India; urea; and calcium ammonium nitrate plus P and K. N is in the form of NH₄Cl in mixture A and (NH₄)₂SO₄ in mixture B. The shortfall in N and K were adjusted with urea and muriate of potash. All P and K were applied at transplanting. Treatments received 50% N at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

Grain yield was highest with N as NH₄Cl (3.8 t/ha) (see table). N as

Direct and residual effects of micronutrients on rice and wheat yields. Keonjhar, Orissa, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Application method	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Rice	Wheat
Control		3.0	1.8
FYM 5 t/ha		3.2	1.9
Zn 4.5 kg/ha	Soil	3.3	1.7
Zn 0.11 mg/liter	Foliar	3.2	2.0
Mn 14.2 kg/ha	Soil	3.0	1.6
Mn 0.18 mg/liter	Foliar	3.1	1.6
Cu 2.5 kg/ha	Soil	3.2	1.8
Cu 0.07 mg/liter	Foliar	3.1	1.5
Fe 10 kg/ha	Soil	2.9	1.5
Fe 0.10 mg/liter	Foliar	3.0	1.8
CD (0.05)		0.1	ns